

Adolescents, e-cigarettes and nicotine: a dangerous interaction

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ABSTRACT Adolescence is a phase of great vulnerability and, due to the diverse characteristics of adolescents, a time of searching for harmful habits such as smoking, alcohol consumption and drugs. In addition to the large modifications that occur through the action of several hormones, all organs and systems undergo structural and functional changes, mainly the central nervous system which, due to their specific characteristics, can suffer severe and definitive compromises. This article presents some characteristics of the development of the central nervous system of the adolescent and the harmful effects of nicotine on the different structures, in addition to the emotional changes caused by the growing addiction of electronic smoking worldwide, especially in the adolescence.

KEYWORDS adolescent, nicotine, electronic cigarette

Introduction

Adolescence is a phase of life characterized by great physical, emotional and social development of human being and a prominent structural and functional brain maturation. Particularly about the development of the central nervous system, adolescence comprises a period of great vulnerability due to the various modifications that occur in the formation and specialization of the structures of the prefrontal cortex and the limbic system, responsible for the control of impulses and emotions [1,2]. The adolescent's brain completes its maturity around the age of 25, and the main changes occurring in the adolescent's nervous system are a synaptogenesis, decrease in gray matter due to the loss of underused synapses, reorganization of the dopaminergic system, relative expression of different neurotransmitter (regions of the brain where dopamine acts undergo significant modifications), increasing in white matter, myelination, and great functional integration, resulting in cortical volume and thickness reductions that are most evident in prefrontal and temporal cortices, as well as subcortical structures [3-5].

The structures that most change during adolescence are the limbic system, mainly amygdala, hippocampus, hypothalamus, prefrontal cortex and nucleus accumbens, associated with a profound reorganization of neural circuitry. The synapses are formed slowly, and the prefrontal cortex (responsible for planning and assessing the risk of decisions, cognitive functions and behavioural control) mature later, reaching full maturation during the third decade of life [3,4,6].

Adolescents have characteristic behaviours such as risk-taking, novelty-seeking, high play and increased social interactions, experience heightened approach motivation, relative to other age groups, towards novel stimuli such as cigarettes, alcohol and drugs and this motivation is difficult to regulate due to the continued development of cognitive control abilities [7]. Neuromaturation, which essentially comprises volume, structure and neurochemistry changes, occurs along with numerous behavioural alterations. Given this, adolescents adopt more favourable attitudes and attributeless social and health risks when they wish to experiment or use various drugs, including cigarettes [8,9].

E-cigarettes

Since 2003 there is an alternative to traditional cigarette smoking, the so-called electronic cigarettes (EC), which came up with the initial aim of trying to reduce the harmful effects of cigarette smoking. Generally referred to as electronic nicotine delivery system, EC is rapidly developing technology which has become widely used in the whole world [10].

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EC are battery-powered devices that produce an aerosol from a solution typically containing nicotine, flavouring chemicals, and other additives. The liquid is heated, creating an aerosol that is inhaled through a mouthpiece by the user. Components of EC solutions generally include nicotine, flavouring chemicals, and other additives [11]. Most e-liquids are composed of varying ratios of propylene glycol and vegetable glycerin, formulate to maximize the subjective sensation of the carried flavouring agents [12]. In addition, these solutions may contain tobacco-specific nitrosamines, tobacco alkaloids (nicotine), metals nanoparticles (cadmium, aluminium, copper, nickel, lead, manganese, chromium, magnesium), arsenic, alcohol, aldehydes, volatile organic compounds, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, carbonyl compounds, solvent carriers and drugs (rimonabant, tadalafil), many of which are toxic and carcinogenic [13-17]. All of these elements can exert cytotoxic effects via oxidative stress and inflammatory changes. Nanoparticles can penetrate deep into the lung parenchyma, reaching the alveolar epithelium, circulatory system, and cell systems where they can cause damage [18]. Due to the condition of heating of liquid of EC in which chemicals reactions could result in the formation of new compounds, the chemical composition of aerosol could be different from the composition contained in liquid [19]. The production of harmful substances is influenced by the battery voltage output, the vaporizer and the levels of e-liquid left in the EC and the higher temperatures are associated with greater nicotine aerosolization [20].

The vapour solution usually consists of propylene glycol or glycerol, nicotine, and flavouring agents [11,21]. Known harmful toxicants and carcinogens have been found in EC emissions. These include polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons as well as nicotine, volatile organic compounds, and fine and ultrafine particles. Superheating of glycol derivatives increases the generation of potentially carcinogenic carbonyl compounds [22-24].

Adolescent and E-cigarettes

The prevalence of EC use is increasing in the whole world, with millions of adolescents annually using this new modality of nicotine consumption [25-27].

Adolescents have a false perception that EC is safe or pose minimal health hazards, less addictive and socially acceptable [28-31]. Among the several factors that lead the adolescent to the consumption of EC should be highlighted advertising via television, movies, Internet, stores, magazines and newspaper with frequent appeals such as used by celebrities, feature cartoons [32,33] and ease of purchase in tobacco shops, pharmacies, grocery and convenience stores. Curiosity, delight flavours, friends' use (peer influence) good flavors, does not smell bad, can hide it from adults, low cost and to reduce stress are also related to the demand for EC [30].

Because EC is perceived as fashionable and more healthy than combustible cigarettes, they seem to attract young people who are slightly elevated on risk status but not initially likely to engage in a lifestyle of substance use [25,34,35].

Longitudinal studies have reported that EC use is associated with an increased risk of cigarette smoking initiation among never cigarette-smoking adolescents and young adults even after adjusting for known demographic, psychosocial, and behavioural risk factors. Smoking initiation is most likely to occur during adolescence and adolescents are more likely than other ages to continue smoking due to the increased positive effects induced by nicotine during this developmental period [4].

Health effects of e-cigarettes

Inhalation of EC aerosol is not safe. There are many varieties of EC, and each brand varies in the concentration of nicotine and additions, and some products have not been studied as an inhalant or for long-term use and heating process to vaporize the solution [11]. The toxicity may be affected by factors like a content, dosage, duration, concentration, frequency, age of exposure, and due to nicotine, which reaches airways, lungs and cardiovascular system [36].

Besides causing increase oxidative stress, neuronal apoptosis, and deoxyribonucleic acid damage, several other problems were related to nicotine, such as [19,37-41]:

1. throat irritation, increased salivation, cough and phlegm;
2. decreased forced expiration volume in 1 second;
3. alterations in the metabolism of bronchial epithelial cells; changes in lung fibroblasts;
4. exacerbation of asthma and bronchitis;
5. inflammatory changes in organ development and mucous membrane functions;
6. tachycardia, hypertension, hypothermia, nausea, diaphoresis;
7. increase blood viscosity, hypercoagulable state;
8. increase in plasma free fatty acids;
9. interference in sleep cycles;
10. , risk of cancer development by affecting gene expression in different organs;
11. risk of fires, explosions, and toxicity due to high concentrations of nicotine in the cartridges;

Effects of nicotine

Nicotine is the major psychoactive component of EC solution. The amount of nicotine present in electronic cigarettes may reach from 18 mg/mL (1,8%) to over 59 mg/mL (5%). It is a potent stimulant and parasympathomimetic alkaloid, of the organic group of the amines, mainly found in tobacco leaves. Because it is a weak base, its absorption across biological membranes is pH dependent and can be absorbed through the skin. The large surface area provided by the small airways and the alveoli, associated to pH of 7,4 of the lungs, allow rapid absorption of inhaled nicotine and transition to the brain within 6 - 10 seconds, were exerts its pharmacological effects by binding to the nicotine acetylcholine receptors and triggering release of dopamine and other neurotransmitters [42]. The brain half-live of nicotine is 52 minutes.

Nicotine increases dopamine concentrations and activates the nucleus accumbens, amygdala, thalamus, limbic system and frontal cortical lobe [41,43,44]. These actions can lead to the disruption of neural circuit development with long-term cognitive and behavioural impairment.

Nicotine users endorse a reduction in pain, anxiety, and other negative emotional symptoms along with positive feelings of mild euphoria, alertness, increased memory, and learning [45,46]. Nicotine induces proliferation of vascular smooth muscle cells

and the migration of cells into blood vessels, and increases lipolysis, resulting in the release of free fatty acids; over time, these effects cause an acceleration of coronary and peripheral vascular disease as well as an increase in the risk of strokes. Nicotine may increase the risk of oral, oesophageal, and pancreatic cancer [47,48].

The hypothalamus is one of the regions of the brain responsible for the homeostatic control of energy, whereas the mesolimbic dopaminergic neurons, involved with emotion and motivation, is related to the hedonic aspects of food intake. Some studies have shown that nicotine inhibiting food and that those effects are the result of the modulatory effect of nicotine on both metabolic processes and reward circuits [49,50]. Possible reductions in essential nutrient intake during adolescence can also lead to impairments in growth and development. The liver metabolizes almost 90% of nicotine, and the metabolites are excreted through the kidneys, faeces, sweat, breast milk, and saliva. The rate of nicotine metabolism may vary by race, sex and genetic expression of enzymes. The elimination half-life of nicotine is 2 to 3 hours [14,26,51].

Flavours are used and marketed to increase product appeal and palatability of EC. There is an extensive range of flavors (fruit, cotton candy, cream soda, dessert, etc) available on the current market, which are used as an incentive for experimentation by adolescents [52]. Many of the flavouring chemicals contain aldehyde, a respiratory irritant, in sufficient concentration to be of toxicologic concerns [16,53,54]. Menthol, a widely used flavouring agent, has anaesthetic properties which reduced perceived hardness and irritation of smoke, produce increase respiratory frequency, a higher respiratory volume, interferes in the metabolism of nicotine increasing its bioavailability and absorption by the mouth, and deeper smoke inhalation [17].

Nicotine and adolescent brain

The sensitivity of the brain to the aggressions of environmental agents depends on their state of development. Nicotine hurts adolescent brain development. Human brain development continues far longer than was previously realized, and nicotine use during adolescence has been associated with deleterious effects on development in the prefrontal cortex and hippocampal structure, can lead to irreversible decreased cognitive function, mainly attention, memory and hyperactivity, and severe addiction [55,56].

Nicotine has neurotoxic effects on the developing brain by blocking dopamine uptake and increasing synaptic dopamine release, causing a variety of physiological effects as neural activation and behavioural arousal. Increased dopamine levels may enhance the behavioural effects of nicotine, producing a pleasurable state and interference in the brain's reward system. When dopamine levels fall, the adolescent is bound to seek more nicotine, leading to a vicious cycle that has just turned into addiction [57]. Another mechanism of action of nicotine occurs by blocking of the gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), a potent inhibitor of some brain systems, including that of reward [58].

Nicotine exposure during adolescence activates hippocampal nicotinic acetylcholine receptors during this sensitive period, disturbing these mechanisms to produce persistent morphological (diminished cortical surface area and reduced hippocampal volume), functional, and behavioural hippocampal dysfunction [59,60].

The hippocampus is a structure associated with emotion, memory and adult neurogenesis. Given the anatomical and

functional characteristics found during the second decade of life, adolescents have potentially increased sensitivity to nicotine, developing symptoms of dependence at lower levels of exposure than adults. The younger the age of smoking initiation, the more likely an individual will become dependent on tobacco in adulthood and more difficult to quit [2,26,61,62].

What should we do

Health promotion and disease prevention are missions that must mobilize the whole society. In this way, many actions can be taken to reduce the damages caused by smoking. Some of the key measures should include [11,29,55,63-65]:

1. individual education and information to provide anticipatory guidance regarding high-risk behaviours, safety and the potential health risks of EC;
2. mass media campaigns with health warnings;
3. state tobacco control: smoke-free air laws, legislation that prohibits the marketing and sales of EC to youth, control of tobacco using in television and films, increasing taxes; ban all characterizing flavours in EC, control of Internet sales of EC and EC solutions.

Summary

In the 21st century, many people are still not well informed about the harmful effects of smoking and nicotine. Smoking, in any form, is a complex phenomenon that is affected by many factors, and the use of EC must be evaluated as a potential medium and long-term health risk [66]. Research and dissemination on the risks and health hazards caused by nicotine and other elements present in cigarettes, as well as knowledge about the behavioural characteristics of adolescents are fundamental to combat the progression of this addiction [30]. Major structural remodelling of the brain occurs during adolescence, especially in regions implicated in the maturation of emotional and cognitive control, and the nicotine exposure during this period interferes with the natural course of these processes, leading to long-term changes in neural development [67]. EC must be considered as severe threats to adolescent physical and mental health because they act as a gateway for the consumption of other drugs engages in high-risk sexual behaviour and developed psychiatric disorders [41,68]. Adolescents, usually under the influence of the family social environment and peers, often do not recognize these health risks and the addictive potential of EC [11,69,70]. It is, therefore, time to address the issue with the importance it acquires as one of the major public health problems of our time.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in this study.

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